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Instilling Social Studies Values in Instructional Strategy for Promoting National Unity among Students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the integration of social studies values among the students in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto. Its main goal was to serve as a model for fostering ethno-religious and cultural tolerance among students with aim of promoting national unity. Adopting a descriptive survey method and cross-sectional survey design, the study focused on 816 students of NCE 2 and NCE 3 from the department of social studies. Using a purposive sampling procedure, a sample of 816 students was selected for the study. Data was collected through a questionnaire titled “Instilling Social Studies Values in Instructional Strategy for Promoting National Unity (ISSVISPN) Among Students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto”. The research questions were tested using simple percentages. The results revealed that incorporating social studies values in instructional strategies significantly promotes national unity among students. This highlights the crucial role of social studies values in enhancing ethno-religious and cultural tolerance. The study suggests that other sister departments in the institution should burrow from social studies curriculum in their instructional strategy for the promotion of national unity among the students.

Keywords: Social Studies Values; National Unity; Ethno-Religious Tolerance; Instructional Strategy; Cultural Tolerance

INTRODUCTION

National unity is a fundamental requirement for fostering social cohesion and sustainable development, especially in a diverse country like Nigeria. As one of the most ethnically and culturally heterogeneous nations globally, Nigeria contends with challenges such as ethnic tensions, religious differences, and regional disparities. These issues highlight the necessity of cultivating national unity to ensure peace,

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stability, and collective progress. Education serves as a critical platform for achieving this goal, providing opportunities to instill values that emphasize respect, tolerance, and cooperation among diverse groups. Social studies, as an interdisciplinary field, play a vital role in transmitting these values, making it an indispensable tool for promoting unity (Olawepo, 2020).

Social studies originated in the United States of America in the 1950's. Before the Second World War (1939-1945) it did not exist as a separate subject in the school system. Issues that developed during and after the war led to its introduction as a separate subject in the schools. Below are some of the reasons that led to the development of social studies (Moses, 2018:4-6):

The first reason was to heal the wound caused by the wars by re-establishing and promoting good human understanding and relationships among the peoples of the world. Make peace and reconcile the peoples of the world. Make peace and to reconcile the peoples of the countries that took part in the World Wars to create a better society for humanity.

The second reason for introducing social studies as a subject was to develop a new approach to the solution of problems. After the wars, there were problems of disunity, religious differences, ethnic or racial prejudices and rivalries, crime, poverty, frustration and Medicare. In an attempt to solve these problems in Europe and America, it was observed that most of them were interconnected. It was then realized that in order to solve a problem satisfactorily, it is necessary to identify all the relevant links in the chain of which the problem forms a part. It was discovered that solving a problem in isolation might create other problem which could be worse than what the solution intended to remove. It would therefore be useful to think of the consequences of solving a problem in a particular way, before employing any type of solution. This analytical approach to problem solving is known as integrated approach and is linked with the integrated social studies program.

The third reason was the deficiencies discovered in studying the society through the separate social studies subjects. Before the Second World War, the subjects learn in schools among the social science subjects were separate subjects such as history, geography, political science and economics. After the wars, it was decided that the study of society and its proper understanding could be better taught through and integrate subject that could enlist various aspects of the separate social science subjects. This will help look at the realities of life in their interconnectedness. This line of thought led to curriculum change in the United States and Britain in the 1990's.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to explore the potential impact of the integration of social studies values in teaching methods in promoting national unity among students enrolled in the Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto. This will be achieved considering the following specific objectives:

- To assess the impact of social studies values in promoting national unity among students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto.
- To identify the particular social studies values that are most effective in promoting national unity among the students of the ShehuShagari College of Education, Sokoto.
- To study the use of social studies values as a teaching strategy in departments other than social studies in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto.
- To compare the attitudes of students enrolled in social studies courses with those of students in other departments particularly in terms of showing respect for different cultures, ethnicities, and religious beliefs in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto.

Research Questions

The study addressed the following research questions:

- How does the social studies curriculum at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto contribute to the development of national values and unity among students?
- Which values, taught in social studies classes, are most effective in fostering national unity among students at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto?
- To what extent can the values embodied in social studies be used as effective teaching strategies in other departments at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto?

- What are the differences between students in the Department of Social Studies and those in other departments at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto in terms of showing respect and tolerance towards culture, ethnicity and religious beliefs?

Research Hypotheses

The four (4) hypothetical questions from the research study “Instilling Social Studies Values in Instructional Strategy for the Promotion of National Unity among Students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto” formulated will be tested at 0.05 level of significance in order to answer the research questions:

H1: The social studies curriculum at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto significantly contributes to the development of national values and unity among students.

H2: The values taught in social studies classes are more effective in fostering national unity among students at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto compared to values taught in other subjects.

H3: The values embodied in social studies can be effectively used as teaching strategies in other departments at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto to promote national unity.

H4: There is a significant difference between students in the Department of Social studies and those in other departments at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto in terms of demonstrating respect and tolerance towards culture, ethnic and religious beliefs.

Instilling Social Studies Values as an Instructional Strategy for Promoting National Unity in Nigeria

A nation’s education worldwide not only in Nigeria has been recognized as the catalyst for achieving socio-economic, scientific and technological development (Nonkanyiso, 2024). It also includes development strategies put forward to actualize effective and conducive environment that will bring about improvement in the quality of the people. For instance, Federal Government of Nigeria (2004) declared in this National Policy on Education that education is an instrument par excellence for achieving national development. In other words, any meaningful growth and development of any country must be preceded by a sound education planning. Since education constituted an indispensable aspect of social realities of a nation, it is of cardinal importance to any society (Yakubu, 2020:1). To this extent, social studies education can play a vital role in ensuring that the country attains its national unity. The following are advocated as the most appropriate ways through which social studies education can be repositioned towards promoting national unity in the country:

- ✓ Emphasis on Value Education;

The heightened conflict, instability and general insecurity in Nigeria calls for active integration of values in Nigeria’s social studies curriculum. Baudel (2022) asserted that the value educations in social studies curricular in Nigerian schools are inadequate. The Nigerian social studies education curriculum ought to be improved and enriched with values to mitigate ethnicity, favoritism, intolerance among other vices that have debased our moral integrity, freedom and democratic existence as a dignified nation.

Against this background, Mwasalwiba (2022), contributed as follows:

“What needs to be changed socially is one general attitude to life. This will mean changing from our current intolerance life to life of love. We must take complete U-turn from our present undue attachment to moral Decadence, false sense of value, situation of religious intolerance, social Injustice to a new national reorientation that recognize excellence merit, Dignity and the tolerance of human beings irrespective of his/her ethnic Group as the basis of our values system”.

- ✓ Promotion of Citizenship Education;

Social Studies place much value on promoting good citizenship education in social studies for instance, the effective domain deals with the evaluation of attitude that are developed in the pupils after a course of study. The domain examines behavioral changes in pupils like respect for elders and other constituted authorities as parents, government etc. dignity of caliber and other positive attitudes. Social Studies as a discipline if properly programmed and effectively taught, should help to

solve social problems like kidnapping, raping, murder, corruption etc. and develop a sense of patriotism.

✓ **Emphasis on Peace, Safety and Security Education;**

It is a common knowledge that our society (Nigeria) today is being plagued by evil such as profit tearing, embezzlement, social unrest by the youths and other irresponsible behaviors. Social Studies Education if properly repositioned can help greatly to educate the youths on the importance of peace and security in our dear nation. This will help to promote co-operation and national pride by keeping to the rules and regulations of the country.

✓ **Promotion of Competence and Civic Education;**

Social Studies content should be redesigned to include work ethics, dedication, honesty, national ideas, decision making process and problem solving. Social Studies Education should be made to address the issues that are today confronting the nation. These issues include terrorism, armed robbery, hostage taking; suicide bombing etc. in view of Olayinka (2023) Social Studies should be made to give impetus to positive development trends in Nigeria.

Successful Implementation of Instructional Strategies in Promoting National Unity: Case Studies of Other Educational Institutions

Implementing instructional strategies that promote national unity has been a focus for educational institutions worldwide. Notable case studies and best practices include:

- **Multicultural Education in the United States:** The U.S. education system has emphasized multicultural education to foster national unity. This approach integrates diverse cultural perspectives into the curriculum, promoting inclusivity and mutual respect among students from various backgrounds. By acknowledging and valuing diversity, schools aim to build a cohesive national identity that encompasses all cultural groups (Banks, 2019).
- **Unity Schools in Nigeria:** Nigeria's Federal Government established Unity Schools, also known as Federal Government Colleges, to promote national integration. These schools admit students from different ethnic religious backgrounds, encouraging interaction and understanding among diverse groups. The policy of federal character in admission ensures representation from all regions, fostering a sense of national unity among students (Omede & Agahui, 2016).
- **Social Integration in Malaysian Schools:** Malaysia has implemented programs to enhance social integration among students of different ethnicities. The Ministry of Education developed a Unity Index to measure and promotes unity initiatives within schools. By assessing students' interactions and fostering inclusive activities, Malaysian schools aid to strengthen national cohesion (Khalid et al., 2019).
- **Inclusive Education in Northern Ireland:** In response to cultural diversity, some schools in Northern Ireland have adopted inclusive educational practices. These schools actively promote good relations and social inclusion by integrating students from various backgrounds. Such initiatives aim to build good relations and allow full participation of children, young people, and adults from diverse backgrounds through schools, including incoming minority groups (Ugobueze, 2024).

These examples demonstrate that educational institutions can play a pivotal role in promoting national unity by implementing inclusive curricula, fostering diverse interactions, and adopting policies that encourage social cohesion.

The Unique Cultural and Regional Context of Sokoto and Its Influence on Instructional Strategies

The unique cultural and regional context of Sokoto State plays a critical role in shaping instructional strategies in education. As a predominantly Hausa-Fulani region and a hub of Islamic scholarship, educational approaches in Sokoto must align with local cultural and religious values to effectively engage learners and address community expectations.

Incorporating Religious and Cultural Values: Educational strategies in Sokoto are more effective when they integrate Islamic teachings and reflect local culture practices. This alignment enhances the

relevance of the curriculum, fosters moral development, and promotes active student engagement (Ministry of Education Sokoto, 2010).

Gender-Inclusive Approaches: Given the region's traditional gender roles, strategies that encourage female education while respecting cultural sensitivities are essential. Programs providing financial incentives, such as stipends for families, have proven successful in increasing girls' enrollment and retention in schools (Sokoto Government House, 2017).

Community Involvement: Engaging community leaders and parents in the educational process ensures that instructional methods resonate with local values and receive communal support. This involvement helps foster an environment conducive to learning and collaboration (Creative Associates International, 2016).

Use of Indigenous Languages: Using Hausa, the dominant language in Sokoto, as a medium of instruction for early education enhances students' comprehension and academic performance. This approach respects the linguistic background of the region and promotes better learning outcomes (Ministry of Education Sokoto, 2010).

Addressing Economic Barriers: Given the financial challenges many families face, strategies such as providing free educational materials and school feeding programs have been effective in increasing school attendance and reducing dropout rates (Sokoto Government House, 2017).

By tailoring educational strategies to Sokoto's cultural and regional context, educators can create more inclusive and impactful learning environments. Such strategies ensure that the curriculum respects local traditions while addressing broader educational goals.

Challenges and Limitations Associated with Implementing Instructional Strategies at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto

Implementing culturally responsive instructional strategies at Shehu Shagari College of Education in Sokoto faces several notable challenges and limitations:

Inadequate Resources: The development of culturally responsive curricula requires significant resources, including teaching materials tailored to the local context and adequate trained staff. Limited funding often hampers access to these essential resources, affecting the overall quality of education provided (Ayaz, 2022).

Insufficient Teacher Training: To effectively implement culturally responsive teaching, educators need specialized training that equips them to incorporate students' cultural backgrounds into their instructional methods. However, a lack of professional development opportunities often prevents teachers from adopting these approaches effectively (Ayaz, 2022).

Rigid Curriculum Structures: The rigidity of the existing curriculum poses a challenge, as it may not easily accommodate the integration of culturally relevant content. This inflexibility makes it difficult for educators to adapt teaching methods to reflect the diverse cultural experiences of their students (Ayaz, 2022).

Resistance to Change: Teachers accustomed to traditional instructional methods may resist adopting new culturally responsive strategies, slowing the process of implementation and reducing its effectiveness (Ayaz, 2022).

Overcrowded Classrooms: Large class sizes pose another limitation, as they reduce teachers' ability to address the unique cultural and learning needs of individual students effectively (Ayaz, 2022).

Technological Limitations: The integration of technology in teaching practice is hindered by limited access to digital tools and internet connectivity, which restricts the implementation of innovative and culturally responsive teaching methods (Ayaz, 2022).

Addressing these limitations require targeted interventions such as increased funding, professional development for teachers, curriculum reform, and measures to reduce class sizes. By overcoming these barriers, Shehu Shagari College of Education can create a more inclusive and culturally responsive learning environment.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

The study employs the descriptive survey method, using a cross-sectional survey design which requires that data collected at a particular time from a sample for the purpose of describing the study population presented by the sample at that particular time. This is in consideration of the objective of the study which is to empirically examine the effect of one variable on the other.

Population of the Study

The study will focus on a population of 816 NCE 2 and NCE 3 students drawn from the different Social Studies combinations in the School of Arts and Social Sciences Programmes at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto. Data collection will take place during the **2023/2024** academic year.

Sample Frame and Sampling Techniques

A stratified random sampling technique will be adopted for sample selection to ensuring representation of students from different social studies combinations and across various ages, gender and state of indigenization/origin in Shehu Shagari College of Education so as to purposely serve as a source of the research respondents.

A sample of 816 students will be selected: 454 students (56%) will be drawn from Social Studies Double Major and History/Social Studies students, 362 students (44%) from the Economics/Social Studies, English/Social Studies, Hausa/Social Studies, Islamic Studies/Social Studies and Special Education/Social Studies combinations for the study.

Instrumentation

The research instrument use in the study for data collection and gathering was a researcher developed questionnaire based on five (5) point Likert Scale. The questionnaire was tagged as “**Instilling Social Studies Values in Instructional Strategy for Promoting National Unity questionnaire Among Students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto**” (ISSVPNU). The questionnaire consists of five (5) sections. Section A was designed to seek demographic information of the respondents. Section B; C; D; & E; were used to collect information awareness of Social Studies Values, Effectiveness of Instructional Strategies, Impact on National Unity, Challenges and Recommendations of the respondents. Section (Item) B & C each has 3 statements whereas Section (Item) D & E each has 2 statements, to which the students responded.

Method of Data Collection

The primary approach for gathering data will involve the use of a structured questionnaire on the study “**Instilling Social Studies Values in Instructional Strategy for Promoting National Unity (ISSVISPNU) Among Students of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto**”. This tool will be reviewed and approved by two experts in the field of measurement and evaluation to ensure its validity. Additionally, the Cronbach’s Alpha method will be implemented to assess the reliability of the questionnaire, ensuring its consistency and accuracy. Data will be collected from a diverse group of 816 students from various social studies combinations, including Economics/Social Studies, English/Social Studies, Islamic Studies/Social Studies, Hausa/Social Studies, History/Social Studies, Special Education/Social Studies, and Social Studies Double Major.

Method of Data Analyses

Upon completion of data collection, a thorough analysis will be conducted using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics will be used to address the research questions, while inferential statistics will be utilized to test hypotheses. Simple percentage will be calculated for research questions, while chi-square statistics will be applied for hypotheses testing. All responses will be translated from their original language to the research language, and exact quotes will be used to accurately represent the participants’ views. Furthermore, content analysis will be used to examine the source material.

Results/Expected Output

This study aims to achieve the following results and outcomes:

- Develop a conducive educational environment at S. S. C. O. E, Sokoto, promoting respect for the worth and dignity of all students.

- Instill confidence in students at S. S. C. O.E, Sokoto, empowering them to make informed decisions.
- Foster the moral and spiritual values of students at S. S. C. O. E, Sokoto, promoting positive human interactions.
- Cultivate a sense of shared responsibility among all students, regardless of their tribal, religious, or cultural background.

CONCLUSION

In summary, this research underscores the critical role that instructional strategies play in fostering national unity among students. The literature reveals that approaches such as multicultural education, civic education, and intergroup interactions promote inclusivity, mutual respect, and a shared sense of identity among diverse learners. Social studies education, with its focus on instilling values, fostering citizenship, and emphasizing peace and security, emerges as a powerful avenue for addressing societal challenges, enhancing national pride, and fostering unity.

The persistent challenges to Nigeria's national cohesion, including ethnic and religious divides, historical tensions, and regional inequalities, highlight the pressing need for inclusive and strategic teaching methods. Success stories, such as Nigeria's Unity Schools, the United States' multicultural education initiatives, and integration programs in Malaysia and Northern Ireland, showcase how education can bridge societal divides and cultivate national cohesion.

Therefore, adopting intentional and inclusive instructional strategies is essential to promoting unity in diverse societies. By equipping students with the tools to value diversity and actively participate in nation-building, educators can significantly contribute to creating a more harmonious and unified society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations provide tailored instructional strategies for Shehu Shagari College of Education in Sokoto to promote national unity and enhance student development.

1. *Incorporating Multicultural Education*

- Include diverse cultural perspectives in the curriculum to reflect Sokoto's and Nigeria's ethnic and religious diversity.
- Host cultural exchange programs and events to foster understanding and respect among students from various backgrounds.
- Train educators in culturally responsive teaching methods to ensure inclusivity in the classroom.

2. *Enhancing Civic Education*

- Focus on teaching democratic principles, rights, and responsibilities in social studies courses.
- Engage students in activities like debates, community service, and simulations of democratic processes to promote active civic participation.
- Use Sokoto's socio-political context as a reference to make lessons more relatable and meaningful.

3. *Encouraging Intergroup Contact*

- Organize group activities where students from different ethnic and religious groups collaborate to reduce stereotypes and build teamwork.
- Create mentorship programs that pair diverse students to work together on shared projects.
- Facilitate dialogue sessions and workshops to promote understanding and address biases.

4. *Focusing on Value-Based Education*

- Integrate core national values, such as tolerance, integrity, and patriotism, into the curriculum to address moral challenges.
- Introduce courses on conflict resolution and peaceful coexistence to reduce intolerance and insecurity.
- Use storytelling and case studies to illustrate the importance of unity and shared identity.

5. Prioritizing Peace and Security Education

- Develop peace education initiatives to teach students about conflict resolution and community harmony.
- Partner with local organizations and leaders to deliver seminars on peace building and security.

6. Leveraging Technology

- Use digital tools to support intercultural learning and broaden students' understanding of national unity.
- Create e-learning content that celebrates Nigeria's cultural diversity and emphasizes the benefits of unity.

7. Adopting Collaborative Learning Models

- Encourage students to work in diverse groups, fostering collaboration and shared problem-solving.
- Implement real-world problem-solving activities where students propose solutions to issues affecting national unity.

8. Building Educator Capacity

- Provide teachers with professional development opportunities to learn modern, inclusive instructional strategies.
- Promote active learning methods, such as group discussions, role-playing, and case studies, to make lessons engaging and impactful.

By adopting these strategies, Shehu Shagari College of Education can contribute significantly to fostering national cohesion and preparing students to play constructive roles in Nigeria's development.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, A., & Musa, I. (2018). Teacher education and its role in promoting national unity in Nigeria: A case study of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto. *Journal of Education and Development*, 8(3), 45-56.
- Adedayo, A. O. (2021). Social studies education and national development in Nigeria: An overview. *African Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(2), 101-114.
- Adediran, A. A. (2015). Social Studies education: An imperative for the promotion of cultural values for national integration in Nigeria. *Journal of Research on Humanities and Social Science*, 3(9): 67.
- Adekunle, B. J., & Olusegun., A. J.. (2021). *Effective social studies teaching strategies*.
- Adewole, O., & Adeyemi, B. (2018). Teachers' assessment of non-cognitive learning outcomes in primary Social Studies. *Journal of Curriculum*, 14(3): 107-121.
- Akpan, C. U., &Mbak, I. M. (2016). Social Studies Education and Development of Culture and Values. *Approaches in International Journal of Research Development*. Pp3- 5Vol.10.
- Aktas, F., Pitts, K., & Richards, J. C. (2017). *Cultivating critical thinking, social justice awareness, and empathy among pre-service teachers through online discussions on global citizenship education*. Retrieved December 19, 2024, from <https://journals.sagepub.com>
- Arisi, R. O. (2011). Social Studies Education as Panacea for National Security in Nigeria. *International Multi-Discipline journal*. Ethiopia 5(2): 19. JSSN 1994-9037.
- Ayaz, M. F. (2022). Potentials Challenges of Twenty-First Century Pedagogies in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Social Innovation*, 5(3), 10-18. <https://ejournal.papanda.org/index.php/jesi/article/download/832/499/3153>
- Bakare, M. I. (2024). CRITICAL Perspective on Social Studies education curriculum in Nigeria: Problems and prospect. *World Educators Forum*, 5(1): 263-272.
- Banks, J. A. (2019). *An Introduction to multicultural education* (6th.ed.). Pearson.

- Baudel, T. (2022). *Teaching Values for Stemming Corruption in Social Studies Classroom in Nigeria Secondary Schools*. A paper presented at the 28th Annual National Conference of Social Studies Association of Nigeria (SOSSAN) held at Benue State University, Makurdi, 9th-13th July.
- Birabil, T. S., & Nwadibia, A. (2023). Constraints to the inquiry-teaching of social studies in Nigerian schools. *Education Forum*. 4 (1&2), 25-37.
- Brant, J., Chapman, A., & Isaacs, T. (2016). International Instructional System: Social studies. *The Curriculum Journal*, 27(1), 62-79. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585176.2015.1134340>
- Brooks, D., & Coole, M. (2020). *Security and Safety Management*. A Key Note Address Presented at 2 days Seminar Organized by Life Consulting Lagos on Wednesday 15th October, 2008.
- Chambliss, J. (2016). *Democracy and education: An introduction to the philosophy of education*. Macmillan.
- Coleman, V. (2021). What is (or are) *Social Studies?* *Research Matter*. Department of Education. Issue 32 Cambridge University & Assessment. Pp. 7-9. Retrieved September 14, 2023, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1317445.pdf>
- Creative Associates International. (2016). *All Hands on Deck to Strengthen Education in Northern Nigeria, Says Expert at CIES*. <https://www.creativeassociatesinternational.com/story/hands-deck-strengthen-education-northern-nigeria-says-expert-cies/>
- Daniel & Baldado (2023). *Invitation to fundamental of teaching Social Studies*.
- Decuir, E. (2012). *Social Studies Reform 1880-1980*.
- Durkheim, E. (2018). *The elementary forms of religious life*.
- Edinyang, S. D. (2015). *Social studies for Colleges and Universities in Nigeria* (Ed). Calabar: Brain Press and Editorial Consultancy.
- Enache, A. (2023). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice-Hall.